

PREVALENCE AND FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH BREASTFEEDING IN THE 1st HOUR OF LIFE AT THE PROFESSOR ALBERTO ANTUNES UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL IN 2017.

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Abstract

Abstract Breastfeeding in the first hour of life is a key factor in reducing neonatal mortality rates, besides providing an initial contact that favors the establishment of the mother-child bond, bringing physical and psychological benefits to both. The research aims to analyze the prevalence and factors associated with breastfeeding in the first hour of life at the University Hospital Professor Alberto Antunes in the year 2017. The study is a documentary, descriptive with a quantitative approach. The result showed that, according to the WHO classification, the rate of breastfeeding in the first hour of life is considered good at the study site. And the factor that has the greatest influence on the accomplishment of this good neonatal practice is the way of parturition. Faced with this reality and the innumerable benefits that this action provides both the mother and the newborn, it is suggested the encouragement of professional training, alternatives for the implementation of this good practice in cesarean parturitions, and the preparation of booklets presenting the main advantages of early maternal breastfeeding.

Keywords: Breastfeeding, First hour of life, Newborn.

INTRODUCTION

Breastfeeding in the first hour of life is recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO), and corresponds to the fourth step of the Baby-Friendly Hospital Initiative (IHAC). This is one of the fundamental strategies for the promotion, protection, and support of breastfeeding in the country, and it is based on the ability of

newborns (NB) to interact with their mothers in the first minutes of life. (BOCCOLINI et al., 2010).

The advantages of early contact between mother and child are numerous (if both are in good health), including it favors the establishment of the mother-child bond, bringing physical and psychological benefits for both. With this contact, the baby stays warm through the mother's

body heat, which prevents hypothermia, helps in the adaptation of the fetal-neonatal transition, and favors the colonization of the newborn's intestine by microorganisms from the maternal skin flora, providing to the neonate greater immunity. In addition, it also provides the NB with efficient and effective suction, which results in an increase in the prevalence and duration of lactation and a decrease in the neonatal mortality rate. (BARBOSA et al., 2010).

The benefits aren't just for the newborn; the woman, too, presents its advantages by starting breastfeeding early.:

[...] a produção hormonal, desencadeada pelo estímulo deste contato, também afeta a saúde da mulher, visto que facilita as trocas fisiológicas da condição de grávida para puérpera e ajuda, em menor tempo, a dequitação da placenta, por ação da ocitocina e dos movimentos que o RN realiza com os pés no ventre materno, o que acarreta a diminuição do risco de hemorragia pós-parto, além de proporcionar menor risco de câncer de mama em decorrência da amamentação. (FERREIRA D'ARTIBALE;BERCINI, 2014).

A survey published on the UNICEF website in July 2016 shows that around 77 million newborns are not breastfed in their first hour of life. The longer the initiation of breastfeeding is delayed, the greater the risk of death in the first month of life. Delaying breastfeeding between 2 and 23 hours after birth increases the risk of death in the first 28 days of life by 40%. Delaying it for 24 hours or more increases this risk by 80%. In Brazil, of the total number of deaths among children under 1 year of age, 65.6% occur in the neonatal period and 49.4% in the first week of life. (UNICEF BRASIL, 2016).

Neonatal mortality (between zero and 27 days of life) is responsible for almost 70% of deaths in the first year of life, and newborn care has been one of the challenges to reduce infant mortality rates in our country from causes considered to be preventable, such as infection, birth asphyxia and complications of prematurity (BRASIL, 2014a).

In this sense, the Ministry of Health (MS) organized a major strategy, the Rede Cegonha, launched in March 2011, and it is a pioneering initiative that aims to achieve many goals, including reducing the number

of preventable deaths from women and children in the country (BRASIL, 2011a). The Stork Network is supported by the PNH (National Humanization Program) and aims to implement health actions capable of producing humanized care within the scope of the Unified Health System (SUS), as well as ensuring that all newborns are good. care practices, based on scientific evidence and humanization principles.

If the newborn is born uneventfully, we have the opportunity to highlight several simple, inexpensive, evidence-based practices that can improve survival rates and are capable of longterm impact on nutrition and health. They are late clamping of the umbilical cord, immediate effective skin-to-skin contact by the mother and newborn, and early initiation of exclusive breastfeeding (BRASIL, 2011b).

Pillegi et al. (2008) emphasize that breastfeeding in the first hour of life can be interfered with by hospital practices and the use of modern technology. According to UNICEF (2009), requiring the mother to lie down during labor and delivery, lack of encouragement and freedom to eat or drink, a separate mother from baby and, most importantly, intervene with unnecessary routine care, such as continuous fetal monitoring, venipuncture, sedative analgesics, and episiotomy, can impair the immediate contact between the mother and the newborn, making it difficult to start breastfeeding.

Analgesics received by the mother during childbirth can decrease the NB's sucking reflex, as they can make them more sleepy, thus reducing milk intake and increasing the risk of jaundice, hypoglycemia, and low weight gain. Generally, NB from mothers who did not receive sedation during the delivery present, soon after birth, a calm state of alertness of around forty minutes. After an hour and a half, these states are no longer so long. (PILLEGI et al., 2008).

The support of a caregiver during labor and delivery can reduce the perception of pain and stress, consequently reducing the need for medical interventions. The help and encouragement of mobility that this can provide increases the mother's confidence, speeding up the labor (UNICEF, 2009).

Despite the existence of several programs to encourage breastfeeding in the 1st hour of life, there is a high rate of mothers who do not breastfeed their newborns early, despite having all the requirements for

this practice. A study carried out with parturients in maternity hospitals in Rio de Janeiro, between 1999 and 2001, showed that only 16% of mothers offered their breasts to newborns in delivery rooms (BOCCOLINI, 2011). Thus, the study aims to verify the prevalence and factors associated with breastfeeding in the 1st hour of life at Professor Alberto Antunes University Hospital in 2017.

METHODS

This study is a documentary analysis, descriptive with a quantitative approach, where data were collected through searches in electronic medical records and birth records of the Maternity Hospital of the University Hospital Professor Alberto Antunes, in Maceió - AL, Brazil. From the survey of information, it was possible to carry out a descriptive analysis of the prevalence and factors associated with breastfeeding in the 1st hour of life in that maternity hospital. To carry out the analysis, the number of patients who breastfed in the 1st hour of life and the associated factors (place of birth, maternal age, gestational age, parity, type of delivery, presence) were verified through a case history of companion at the time of delivery, the weight of the newborn and the fate of the newborn after delivery), in 2017.

The data collected made it possible to create variables related to the problem, allowing for statistical analysis. The criteria for inclusion in this research were: medical records of women whose children were born in the delivery room or in the Obstetric Center of HUPAA and records in which the fetuses were born without serious anomalies. The exclusion criteria were: medical records of women with restrictions on breastfeeding (seropositive), medical records of women with intrauterine fetal death, and records of fetuses with severe malformations. After applying these criteria, we reached a total sample of 1217 medical records (n= 1217).

This study complied with Resolution 466/2012 and 510/2016 of the National Health Council and was initiated after approval on the Plataforma Brasil website, approved under opinion number: 2,442,674. It was not necessary to use informed consent.

RESULTS

The research sought to demonstrate, through numbers, the prevalence and factors associated with breastfeeding in the 1st hour of life, emphasizing its relationship

with maternal age, place of birth (Obstetric Center or Delivery Room), Gestational Age (preterm, term, or postterm), maternal parity (primiparous or multipregnant), type of delivery (cesarean or normal), presence of a companion at the time of delivery and newborn weight (low weight, normal or macrosomic weight).

The study included 1217 births in the maternity hospital of the Professor Alberto Antunes University Hospital (HUPAA), throughout 2017.

Graph 1 shows that, of the total of 1217 births, 793 newborns were breastfed in the 1st hour of life, corresponding to 65% of the total; and 424 were not offered the breast in the 1st hour of life, equivalent to 35%.

Graph 1 - Prevalence of newborns who were breastfed in the 1st hour of life, at HUPAA, in 2017.

Source: (Researcher data, 2018).

At the Professor Alberto Antunes University Hospital, births can take place in two places: at the Obstetric Center and the Delivery Room. Births at the Obstetric Center are usually cesarean deliveries where the indication for surgery is due to maternal and/or fetal health conditions; the normal deliveries that occur at the Obstetric Center are of fetuses with less than 34 weeks (premature) that need more advanced support of care at birth. In the Delivery Room, only normal deliveries of fetuses above 34 weeks are performed, without anomalies, and both mother and child do not have contraindications for this type of birth.

Graph 2 - Consolidated of newborns who were breastfed in the 1st hour of life, according to a place of birth, at HUPAA, in 2017.

Source: (Researcher data, 2018).

The data in Graph 2 show that there were 863 births (71%) in the Obstetric Center and 354 (29%) in the Delivery Room. As for breastfeeding in the 1st hour of life, deliveries in the Delivery Room had a percentage of 82% of adherence to this good neonatal practice, while in the Obstetric Center it was only 58%.

In Graph 3, we observe that 233 pregnant women who gave birth at the study site are in the adolescent age group, corresponding to 19.1% of all pregnant women, and that, despite their young age, the vast majority, 162 (70%), she fed her children in the first hour of life with breast milk. In the other age groups, there was a variation of 61% – 66% in the breastfeeding rate in the 1st hour of life.

Graph 3 - Consolidated of newborns who were breastfed in the 1st hour of life, according to maternal age, at HUPAA, in 2017.

Source: (Researcher data, 2018).

According to maternal parity, we observed that both primiparas and multiparas varied between 68% - 63%, respectively, in breastfeeding in the 1st hour of life, with no major divergences related to this factor, as shown in Graph 4.

Graph 4 - Prevalence of newborns who breastfed in the 1st hour of life, according to maternal parity, at HUPAA, in 2017.

Source: (Researcher data, 2018).

In terms of breastfeeding in the 1st hour of

life (Graph 5), the normal delivery route has a percentage of 81% (410) compared to the cesarean delivery route of 54% (383). Some authors, such as Pillegi (2008), have already shown in their studies that, with scientific progress and discoveries in the field of asepsis, surgery, anesthesia, antibiotic therapy, and blood transfusion, hospital risks have decreased and interventions have expanded, resulting in a progressive increase in cesarean sections, creating hospital routines that promoted the separation of mother and newborn soon after birth, hurting breastfeeding (PILLEGI et al., 2008).

Graph 5 - Consolidated of newborns who were breastfed in the 1st hour of life, according to the type of delivery, at HUPAA, in 2017.

Source: (Researcher data, 2018).

Scientific evidence shows that the presence of a companion contributes to the improvement of health and well-being indicators for the mother (pain relief, shorter duration of labor, and a decrease in the rate of postpartum depression) and the newborn, in addition to the increase in affective bonds (MERIGHI, 2007).

Graph 6 shows that the study's maternity hospital guarantees Law 11.108/2005, as 998 (82%) women gave birth in the presence of a companion of their own choice; as well as the percentage of newborns who were offered the breast in the 1st hour of life was higher in the presence of a companion, 67% (673) than without a companion at the time of delivery, 55% (121).

Graph 6 - Consolidated of newborns who breastfed in the 1st hour of life, according to the presence of the companion at the time of delivery, at HUPAA, in 2017.

Source: (Researcher data, 2018).

Graph 7 shows the consolidated number of newborns who were breastfed in the 1st hour of life according to the classification of preterm, term, and post-term. Preterm babies had a rate of 51% (138) in terms of breastfeeding in the 1st hour of life. The vast majority of births were term newborns, 77.2% (940), with a percentage of 69% (653) for breastfeeding in the 1st hour of life. The only classification in which the breastfeeding rate was less than 50% was that of post-term newborns, with a rate of nonadherence to this good practice of 67% (04).

Graph 7 - Consolidated of newborns who were breastfed in the 1st hour of life, according to gestational age, at HUPAA, in 2017.

Source: (Researcher data, 2018).

In terms of breastfeeding in the 1st hour of life about fetal weight, the prevalence was positive for all classifications of newborns, with a percentage of 54% (108) for low birth weight newborns, 68% (628) for newborns of adequate weight, and 59% (55) for macrosomic, according to Graph 8.

Graph 8 - Consolidated of newborns who breastfed in the 1st hour of life, according to fetal weight, at HUPAA, in 2017.

Source: (Researcher data, 2018).

A study carried out in Recife at a Hospital Amigo da Criança, in 2016, by Silva et al., presented some results similar to those achieved by this research. The rate of breastfeeding in the 1st hour of life was lower (28.7%). Primiparous women also had a higher rate of early breastfeeding (29.3%) than multiparous women.

The type of delivery also showed a significant difference, with normal delivery as a protective factor for breastfeeding, with a percentage of 35.4%, and cesarean delivery with 20.2%. Adequate newborn weight was also positively associated with the outcome of breastfeeding in the 1st hour, with 31.4% (SILVA et al., 2018).

A study by Belo et al. with 562 mothers and newborns, in a Baby-Friendly Hospital in Pernambuco, tried to identify the prevalence of breastfeeding in the first hour of life, the associated factors, and the reasons for its nonoccurrence. The authors obtained as a result that the prevalence of breastfeeding in the 1st hour of life was 31%. And the reasons why 388 children had not been breastfed were: child health problems arising from prematurity and low weight (84.5%) (BELO et al., 2014).

CONCLUSION

The study allowed careful analysis of the prevalence rates and factors associated with breastfeeding in the 1st hour of life at Professor Alberto Antunes University Hospital, in 2017. The results achieved revealed a percentage of 65% in breastfeeding rates, with 793 newborns breastfed in the 1st hour of life, out of a total of 1217 births. Maternal factors such as age and parity did not interfere with breastfeeding. Normal birth and the presence of a companion positively favored this good practice with rates of 81% and

67%, respectively.

Factors linked to newborns, such as prematurity and post-date, are factors that limit breastfeeding in the 1st hour of life, with rates of 51% and 33%, respectively. While children born at term achieve 69% success in this good neonatal practice. Another variable was fetal weight, children with adequate weight had a prevalence of 68%, while those who were born with low weight, and most of the time, needed interventions, had only 54%.

The Professor Alberto Antunes University Hospital is a teaching hospital that helps with academic training and launches a large number of health professionals into the job market. This percentage reached in the survey of 65% in the rate of breastfeeding in the 1st hour of life symbolizes an alert to the need for greater commitment and effectiveness on the part of the entire multidisciplinary team since both the levels recommended by the Ministry of Health (100 %) and by WHO (90-100%) were not reached.

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